

A Study of a New Benzidine Chromithiocyanate Compound

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The analysis and IR evidence conclude the empirical formula as $[C_6H_4NH_3]_3Cr(SCN)_6 \cdot 6H_2O$ of lilac coloured complex compound formed between benzidine acetate and potassium chromithiocyanate which gives another green compound of unknown composition on heating to 200° in air.

In earlier communications^{1,2} the formation of compounds between potassium chromithiocyanate and pyridine, picolines and cyclohexylamine have been reported. We now report on the benzidine chromithiocyanate of empirical formula $[C_6H_4NH_3]_3 Cr(SCN)_6 \cdot 6H_2O$ supported by IR evidence.

EXPERIMENTAL

Potassium chromithiocyanate was prepared and standardised as reported in earlier papers^{1,2}. Pure benzidine was dissolved by warming to 50° in strong acetic acid. After cooling and diluting with a little of water, a slight excess of potassium chromithiocyanate in water ($M/50$) was added. Benzidine chromithiocyanate, a lilac coloured powder, was obtained in dry state after washing with cold water till free from colour of potassium chromithiocyanate and was analysed [Found : SCN, 44.12; Cr, 0.068% $[C_6H_4NH_3]_3 Cr(SCN)_6 \cdot 6H_2O$ requires SCN, 44.23; Cr, 0.066%].

Fig. 1

* Empirical formula wt. of anhydrous state

1. M. P. Gupta and M. L. Anand, *This Journal*, 1966, **43**, 765; 1967, **44**, 270.
2. M. L. Anand, *ibid.*, 1967, **44**, 545.

Effect of temperature and solubility: Benzidine chromithiocyanate, lilac coloured compound, turns reddish-green with loss in weight on heating for $\frac{1}{2}$ to 1 hr. in oven at 120° . But after placing in air the compound regains its original colour and weight. The loss and gain in weight is due to water of crystallisation. After heating for more than an hour at $125-50^\circ$, the compound with further loss in weight turns green which remains as such even when placed in humid atmosphere.

The compound is insoluble in water, ether, CS_2 , *n*-butyl acetate but soluble in alcohol and *n*-tributyl phosphate. It forms an oily layer in acetone which partially dissolves on standing. The compound heated to 200° (green in colour) is insoluble in alcohol, acetone, *n*-tributyl phosphate, acetyl acetone, benzene, cold $4N$ -NaOH and $4N$ -HCl.

Absorption and IR spectra: In order to show the effect of benzidine on the dissociation of chromithiocyanate ion, the absorption of benzidine chromithiocyanate and potassium chromithiocyanate in 95% alcohol and *n*-tributyl phosphate has been measured by H-760

Spekker Absorptiometer in the visible range at different hours (Figs. 1 and 2). The variation in % transmittance against hours at wavelengths 465, 545, 605 and 675 m μ has been plotted of the above solutions (Figs. 3 and 4).

Fig. 4. Effect of time on Potassium Chromithiocyanate (M/1000) at wave lengths - A-A' 465 m μ c.c' 605 m μ - B-B' 545 m μ D-D' 675 m μ

Absorption spectra of potassium chromithiocyanate and benzidine chromithiocyanate with and without heating to 200° for 2 hrs. in KBr phase in the region 700 to 4000 cm⁻¹ were obtained (curves 1, 2 and 3 respectively in Fig. 5).

DISCUSSION

Benzidine acetate with potassium chromithiocyanate gives benzidine chromithiocyanate by replacing potassium with benzidinium group in the manner :

The compound dissociates on standing with time in 95% alcohol and also in *n*-tributyl phosphate under ordinary conditions. In alcohol there is decrease in % transmittance and $\lambda_{\max}$ shifting towards longer wavelength but not to that extent in *n*-tributyl phosphate even in the first few hours of dissolution (Fig. 1). Bjerrum³ has observed that salts of $\text{Cr}(\text{SCN})_3^{3-}$ can be preserved indefinitely in the solid state; in alkaline, acidic or neutral solutions they decompose. When the % transmittance of potassium chromithiocyanate in 95% alcohol and *n*-tributyl phosphate against time is compared with that of benzidine chromithiocyanate similar changes are noticed. But $\lambda_{\max}$ shifting to higher wavelength is less comparatively (Fig. 2). On heating benzidine chromithiocyanate to 150° or above the properties are no more the same. Now the compound is insoluble in alcohol, *n*-tributyl

Fig 5-

phosphate and even in NaOH or HCl showing some change in composition. When IR spectra of benzidine-chromithiocyanate with and without heating to 200° are compared some changes are observed. Peak at 1500 cm^{-1} is split into two. Some peaks which are pretty sharp in without heated compound have become broadened in the heated compound. Water loss is evident. NH_3^+ stretching is almost invisible in the heated compound (Fig. 5). Further work is in progress.

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